

Inter-code Comparison of Time Independent Pulsed Sphere Benchmark Results

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INTRODUCTION

To validate models and simulations, including Monte Carlo neutron transport codes, results are often compared against credible experiment data. Inter-code comparisons can also be useful for finding coding errors and exploring algorithmic features. The pulsed sphere experiments [1, 2] performed at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) can be, and have been, used to validate Monte Carlo codes. These problems are appropriate for validation because they are geometrically simple, involve few materials and are well documented, while complex enough to challenge sophisticated features of radiation transport codes. Measurements are available for experiments involving approximately 20 different materials and have been used for assessing nuclear data libraries and validating Monte Carlo codes such as Mercury and MCNP [3, 4, 5, 6]. One important feature of these experiments is the time-of-flight measurements, which are also very attractive in the validation of time-dependent simulations.

The Center for Exascale Monte Carlo Neutron Transport (CEMeNT) is interested in advancing time-dependent Monte Carlo neutron transport capabilities. One research goal is to implement and evaluate time-dependent transport capabilities in Shift [7], a Monte Carlo code developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL). The pulsed sphere experiments are useful for the validation of steady-state and time-dependent transport algorithms, and they have never before been modeled in Shift in either of these modes. This work presents a comparison of time *independent* Shift-simulated results of several pulsed sphere problems, and comparisons with results from MCNP, Mercury and the measured data distributed with the MCNP validation suite. While these results are not intended to serve as a formal validation of Shift, they do show that Shift produces pulsed spheres simulations that closely compare with those of MCNP and Mercury.

EXPERIMENT SETUP

The experiment setup of the pulsed sphere validation problems consists of spheres of various materials and sizes with a target of tritiated titanium at the center. A beam of 400 keV deuterons irradiates this target, which subsequently produces neutrons from the $T(d,n)^4He$ reaction. These neutrons are nearly isotropic at about 14 MeV, although there is a small energy dependence on the angle from the beam. A pulse of high-energy neutrons is produced that moves outwards through the material undergoing various interactions before being measured. Detectors are positioned at various angles and flight paths ranging from 7.5 to 9.8 meters and observe a spike of uncollided neutrons followed by a spectrum of neutrons that have undergone interactions in the material. This measured data can be valuable in validating neutron cross section libraries and codes. A simplified version of the experiment setup is

shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Simplified experiment setup. [3]

METHODOLOGY

Detailed schematics of the experiment setup allow for accurate models to be created in Monte Carlo codes. In this work, existing files for MCNP and Mercury were used. Eleven MCNP pulsed sphere files are included in the MCNP Shielding Validation Suite. The Mercury input files used were written by Richard "Spike" Procassini at LLNL. The MCNP simulations were run on the Rogue computing cluster at Oregon State University, and the Mercury simulations were executed on Lassen at LLNL.

A version of Shift that includes the Lava library was used to read the MCNP input files into Shift. The Lava library parses all the geometry, materials, and source present in the MCNP input files, and reproduces those models in Shift, providing for consistent comparisons. Tallies in Shift, however, are not converted from MCNP and must be manually defined. At this time, Shift does not have the time-of-flight tally capabilities present in Mercury and MCNP. Instead, energy tallies were defined in Shift and directly compared to energy tallies from the other codes. Due to the flight path of the neutrons to the detector being considerably larger than the radius of the material sphere, the relativistic first flight approximation in Equation 1 can be used to estimate the time of flight from the Shift energy tallies.

$$E = rme \times \left(\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - ((fp)^2 / (t^2 \times c^2))}} \right) - 1 \right), \quad (1)$$

where E is the energy of the neutron [MeV], rme is the rest mass energy of the neutron [MeV], fp is the length of the flight path to the detector [cm], t is the time of flight [ns], and c is the speed of light [cm/ns].

This approximation assumes that the neutron travels at its final energy from the center of the sphere to the detector. The radius of the sphere is typically about 2-10 cm depending on the material while the distance to the detector is typically about 750-1000 cm depending on the detector setup. The original experiments only measured the time of flight but added converted energy tallies using this approximation. More direct comparisons to the experiment data are time-of-flight calculations, however energy tally comparisons can be useful in inter-code comparisons, particularly in codes, like Shift, which produce energy tallies. Data from experiments as well as simulated results from MCNP and Mercury provide a useful standard to compare Shift results with.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Initially, the existing suite of input decks in MCNP version 6.2 for the pulsed sphere experiments were run on the Rogue computing servers at Oregon State University. This suite, provided in the distribution of MCNP, contains models for a variety of experiments from the pulsed sphere sets including spheres of beryllium, carbon, concrete, iron, lead, lithium, nitrogen, plutonium-239, uranium-235, uranium-238, and water. Results from these simulations were compared to data from the experiment. In Figure 2, results for an MCNP simulation of a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere are relatively close to the experiment data.

Fig. 2. 2.9 mfp Carbon Pulsed Sphere, MCNP (10^7 histories) vs Experiment Data.

The uncollided flux that forms the initial peak is very similar to the experiment data for all of the spheres present in the MCNP suite. Materials that caused more scattering such as carbon tended to have less accurate results over the lower energy scattered spectrum that followed the uncollided flux.

Existing Mercury input decks have been created over the years at LLNL primarily by Richard "Spike" Procassini [4, 3]. Input files provided by LLNL were executed on the Lassen supercomputing cluster at LLNL. These Mercury pulsed sphere inputs are similar to those in the MCNP suite, but several represented experiment setups that differed slightly such as the

sphere's diameter and tally type at the detector. A common set of experiments, some of which required modification to ensure the same setup, were simulated and compared between Mercury and MCNP. For example, the input files for a 0.7 mfp U-235 sphere shown in Figure 3 was only available in Mercury with the 26 degree beamline and a flight path of 945.54 cm while the MCNP suite contained the 30 degree beamline and a flight path of 766 cm. Additionally, a different detector was used for the different beamlines and had a slightly different response function. Enough information exists in the input files and literature to add in a detector at the correct location for any beamline and flight path used in the experiments. Recent endeavors have focused on running Mercury with the ENDF/B-VII.1 data that MCNP and Shift were run on. The Mercury model also employs a point detector tally, while the MCNP files used a next event estimator ring detector. Work is ongoing to understand the differences between the results from the various codes, and to reduce the discrepancies in the various modeling approaches. A comparison of time-of-flight results of a U-235 pulsed sphere (0.7 mfp) is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. 0.7 mfp U-235 Pulsed Sphere, Mercury (10^7 histories) vs MCNP (10^7 histories) vs Experiment Data

The results from Mercury compare very well to the experimental data and with results from MCNP, particularly for spheres with lower scattering such as U-235.

A major focus of this research was to produce and compare results using Shift which has never simulated the pulsed sphere problems before. Shift does not have next-event point and ring detector capabilities like MCNP and Mercury, so a cell volume tally was placed in the geometry. This cell was extended in a ring similar to the MCNP ring detector to take advantage of the symmetry of the problem and reduce computational cost. The detector cell covers a very small solid angle, so significantly more histories are needed in Shift compared to the MCNP ring detector. Shift simulations employed ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data. Results from all eleven of the spheres included in the MCNP Validation Shielding Suite were simulated with Shift. For simplicity, only an iron sphere is

shown here as an example, but results from multiple other spheres have been compared to both MCNP and Mercury with similar results. Figure 4 shows energy spectra results from MCNP and Shift while Figure 5 portrays Shift time-of-flight results with the energy bins converted to time bins by the relative first flight approximation in Equation 1.

Fig. 4. 0.9 mfp Iron Pulsed Sphere, MCNP (10^7 histories) vs Shift GG (10^{10} histories)

Fig. 5. 0.9 mfp Iron Pulsed Sphere, MCNP (10^7 histories) vs Shift (10^{10} histories) vs Experiment Data

In general, Shift produced small discrepancies in the scattered spectrum, but the error is typically on a similar order of magnitude as the other codes over most of the spectrum. The differences in tallies used in the various codes may also be contributing to some of the variation in results from code to code.

CONCLUSIONS

The LLNL pulsed sphere experiments possess many desirable qualities for evaluating nuclear data and testing Monte Carlo codes, particularly where time dependent simulation is a factor. While all the simulations included in this work are time *independent*, they provide the same results that a time dependent simulation should produce. The results from MCNP, Mercury, and Shift were generally consistent with each other as well as experiment data when modeling spheres of a variety of materials. Shift was used for the first time to simulate the pulsed sphere experiments and was successful in producing accurate results. Differences in modeling techniques will continue to be eliminated to ensure the highest quality of results for comparisons. In the future, results from time dependent simulations of the pulsed spheres from codes such as Shift can be compared to the time independent simulations in this work.

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